

1 Periodic invasions of BC by the lined shore crab, *Pachygrapsus*
2 *crassipes*, following El Niño events and forecasted effects of a
3 permanent range extension on poorly-dispersing indigenous prey species
4 (*Littorina* spp.)¹

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28 Periodic invasions of BC by the lined shore crab, *Pachygrapsus crassipes*, following El Niño
29 events and forecasted effects of a permanent range extension on poorly-dispersing indigenous
30 prey species (*Littorina* spp.)

31 E. G. Boulding*, S. Behrens Yamada, S. S. Schooler, and A. L. Shanks

32 Abstract:

33 Coevolutionary arms races between shelled gastropods and their predators are more escalated
34 near the equator. Consequently, temperate gastropods are predicted to be maladapted to more
35 tropical shell-crushing crabs. The northern geographical limit of the lined shore crab
36 (*Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840) does not usually overlap with the southern limit of a
37 periwinkle (*Littorina sitkana* Philippi, 1846) that lacks a pelagic larval stage. Large El Niño
38 events increased the winter abundance and poleward transport of *P. crassipes* larvae from
39 California in the Davidson Current. Temporary intertidal crab populations that included females
40 with eggs, were observed 1.5 to 3 years later, >1000 km north of its usual geographical range.
41 Laboratory experiments showed that *L. sitkana* did not have a size refuge from adult *P.*
42 *crassipes*. Moreover, consumption rates of adult *L. sitkana* by *P. crassipes* were ten-fold higher
43 than those published for indigenous purple shore crabs, *Hemigrapsus nudus* (Dana, 1851), with
44 similar claw sizes. The upper intertidal limit of invading *P. crassipes* was higher than that of *H.*
45 *nudus*. Therefore, the invasion of *P. crassipes* reduced the width of *L. sitkana*'s spatial refuge
46 from predation. The permanent presence of this subtropical predator could reduce the intertidal
47 distribution of this temperate gastropod thereby causing contraction of its southern range limit.

48

49 *Key words:* Lined shore crab, *Pachygrapsus crassipes*, range expansion, El Niño, larval
50 transport, Davidson Current, predation, Sitka periwinkle, *Littorina sitkana*, Barkley Sound,
51 Nootka Sound
52

53 Introduction

54 Poleward range extensions of marine predators during periods of climate warming exist in the
55 fossil record and are correlated with extinction events of their prey (Vermeij 1987; Leighton
56 2002; Reddin et al. 2018). Extinctions are thought to occur because coevolution between the
57 shell crushing structures of predators and the calcareous armour of their prey becomes escalated
58 over geological time (Vermeij 1977*a*) and is known to be more escalated in the tropics than in
59 the temperate regions or near the poles (Vermeij 1978, 1987). For example, claw gape, claw
60 propal height, claw mechanical advantage, claw tooth shape, and muscle type have been shown
61 to affect the ability of crabs to generate higher closing forces on larger armoured prey (Warner
62 and Jones 1976; Behrens Yamada and Boulding 1998; Fujiwara and Kawai 2016) which
63 increases the predator's feeding efficiency. Temperate crabs can feed efficiently on small poorly-
64 defended gastropods (Palmer 1985; Webster and Palmer 2018), but only specialist crabs can
65 efficiently feed on thicker-shelled, more ornamented gastropods typical of tropical shores (Zipser
66 and Vermeij 1978; Hughes 1989; Hughes and Elner 1989).

67 Marine predator species with planktotrophic larvae can move poleward at rates several orders
68 of magnitude greater than can indigenous gastropods that lack a larval stage (Sagarin and Gaines
69 2002; Kinlan and Gaines 2003). This difference in dispersal potential may explain why
70 gastropods that possess a pelagic larval stage persist in the fossil record for longer periods of
71 time than species that lack one (Valentine and Jablonski 1986; Gili and Martinell 1994).

72 Inter-annual variation in California Current temperature and currents have profound effects on
73 the geographical distributions of species with pelagic larval stages. The California Current has an
74 undercurrent, the California Undercurrent Current, that rises to the surface and flows poleward
75 towards Vancouver Island during the winter months (Reid and Schwartzlose 1962; Behrens

76 Yamada et al. 2015); this current is known as the Davidson Current (Reid and Schwartzlose
77 1962; Garfield et al. 2013). During strong El Niño events the Davidson Current is faster and
78 warmer which, may explain why temporary northern range expansions of invertebrate and fish
79 species (Percy and Schoener 1987; Sanford et al. 2019) including benthic species (Sellanes et
80 al. 2007; Dawson 2012) occur during El Niño events. For example, the mole crab, *Emerita*
81 *analoga* (Stimpson, 1857), establishes ephemeral populations on the west coast of Vancouver
82 Island, and even on Kodiak Island, Alaska when larvae are advected north from source
83 populations in California during strong El Niño events (Hart 1982; Percy and Schoener 1987;
84 Sorte et al. 2001). These *E. analoga* populations persist for a few years until senescence of the
85 adults and then typically disappear until the next incursion of larvae from the south.

86 Here we document a similar ephemeral poleward geographic range extension in a crab - the
87 lined shore crab, *Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840 – that possesses six planktonic feeding
88 larval stages (Schlotterbeck 1976). The first five zoea stages develop in the plankton in neritic
89 regions, whereas the final stage, or megalopa, disperses onshore and molts into intertidal juvenile
90 crabs. We then use laboratory experiments to explore the possible ecological impacts the
91 permanent addition of this species might have on poorly-dispersing local prey species (Barrios-
92 O'Neill et al. 2014; Laverty et al. 2017). We also assess whether a permanent range extension of
93 *P. crassipes* is likely to occur if large El Niño events and the formation of the North Pacific
94 Blob (Cavole et al. 2016; Cornwall 2019), become more frequent.

95 *Pachygrapsus crassipes* has a historical permanent geographical range from southern Oregon
96 to Baja California (Blanchette et al. 2008). It is a common resident of the upper intertidal zones
97 and lives in rock crevices, under rocks and boulders, in tidepools, and inside marsh bank burrows
98 and, in California, requires 3-4 years to become a large adult (48 mm in Hiatt 1948). It is an

99 opportunistic forager, scraping algal films off rocks using the spoon-shaped tips of its chelae,
100 feeding on macro algae such as *Ulva*, *Fucus* and *Endocladia*, carrion, mussels, abalone, snails,
101 limpets, urchins, newly molted crabs, isopods, and fly larvae (Morris et al. 1980; Robles 1982;
102 Lindberg 1985; Lord and Barry 2017).

103 Two lines of evidence suggest that poleward range expansion of *P. crassipes* could result in
104 range contraction of thin-shelled northern mollusks with direct development, such as *Littorina*
105 *sitkana* Philippi, 1846. Firstly, *L. sitkana*'s southern range limit corresponds to the northern
106 range limit of *P. crassipes* (Behrens Yamada 1977a; Morris et al. 1980). Secondly when
107 individual *L. sitkana* were transplanted south of their range into tidepools around Hopkins
108 Marine Station in Pacific Grove, California some individuals survived the winter and early
109 spring but did not survive the summer. Predation by *P. crassipes* on adults, along with
110 desiccation of egg masses and juveniles (Behrens 1972), were implicated in preventing the
111 establishment of permanent populations of *L. sitkana* in California (Behrens Yamada 1977a;
112 Morris et al. 1980).

113 Shanks and Eckert (2005) hypothesize that the life history of *P. crassipes* is adapted for
114 returning most of its planktonic larvae back to the center of its geographic range, in the Southern
115 California Bight. They argue that *P. crassipes* has evolved so that its life history: 1) the timing of
116 larval release, 2) location of where larvae rear, and 3) the duration of larval life, is adapted to the
117 current patterns within the Bight. The combination of an extended breeding season and a long
118 larval duration tends to retain the larvae within the Bight by the large eddies present there;
119 consequently *P. crassipes* does not go extinct in the center of its present geographical range. As
120 ocean conditions change, so that strong El Niño events become more frequent and of longer
121 duration and major ocean heat waves such as the North Pacific Blob become more common

122 (Cavole et al. 2016; Gentemann et al. 2017; Tseng et al. 2017), the long larval duration of *P.*
123 *crassipes* could also aid its poleward range expansion (Pearson and Dawson 2003; Goode et al.
124 2019).

125 The main goal of this study was to answer the following questions: (i) Are observations of *P.*
126 *crassipes* range expansions and local abundances linked to El Niño events? (ii) Is the timing of
127 *P. crassipes* larvae collected in plankton samples from San Diego, California and Coos Bay,
128 Oregon favorable for northward transport in the Davidson Current? (iii) Is *P. crassipes* capable
129 of crushing thin-shelled prey found north of its historical range, such as the Sitka periwinkle,
130 *Littorina sitkana*? (iv) What would be the possible effect of a permanent range expansion of *P.*
131 *crassipes* on northern prey populations?

132 Materials and methods

133 Range expansions of *Pachygrapsus crassipes*

134 In order to test a link between *P. crassipes* range expansions and El Niño events, we tabulated
135 sightings of *P. crassipes* north of Coos Bay, Oregon by reviewing the literature, interviewing
136 biologists and marine educators working in Oregon and Washington, and sampling sites around
137 Bamfield Marine Station (BMSC, 48.8333°, 125.1428°) and in Nootka Sound (49.5234°,
138 126.5719°) on Vancouver Island (Supplementary Table S1). Only the Bamfield site was sampled
139 systematically (1993-2019, Fig. 1). The other sites represent opportunistic sampling from in
140 person and email surveys with biologists and the shellfish industry by SBY. In this manuscript
141 we test whether major northward range expansions were linked to prior El Niño events 1 to 4
142 years earlier. We postulate that time lags in detection of *P. crassipes* occur because juveniles,
143 less than 15 mm in carapace width, are shy and resemble purple shore crabs (*Hemigrapsus nudus*

144 (Dana, 1851)), and therefore may not always be detected by biologists unfamiliar with them
145 (Behrens Yamada, pers. obs.).

146 The Oceanic Niño Index ranks the strength of El Niño warming events based on the
147 temperature anomaly of three consecutive overlapping 3-month periods: weak (+0.5-0.9°C),
148 moderate (+1.0-1.4°C), strong (+1.5-1.9°C), and very strong ($+\geq 2.0^\circ\text{C}$)
149 (<https://ggweather.com/enso/oni.htm>). In addition to warm sea surface temperatures (SST), El
150 Niño events along the west coast of North America are also characterized by an unusually strong
151 northward-flowing Davidson Current during the winter (Reid and Schwartzlose 1962; Behrens
152 Yamada et al. 2015; Tseng et al. 2017). For example, during the 1997-1998 El Niño, northward-
153 flowing currents occurred off Newport, Oregon from September 1997 to April 1998, and
154 averaged 40 km/day for all of January and February 1998 (Kosro 2002). Thus, we hypothesized
155 that strong El Niño events provide a plausible mechanism for transporting *P. crassipes* larvae
156 and other planktonic organisms, from Southern California to Oregon, Washington, and British
157 Columbia (Mackas et al. 2001; Behrens Yamada and Kosro 2010).

158

159 **Sampling of *Pachygrapsus crassipes* adults during long-term field studies at Bamfield**

160 The abundance and size structure of *P. crassipes* has been routinely monitored twice per year
161 as a by-product of a long-term field experiment near BMSC (Bamfield Marine Science Center)
162 that artificially increases the density of purple shore crabs (*Hemigrapsus nudus*) with carapace
163 width (CW) < 20 mm (Boulding et al. 2007). Concrete crab shelters at Nudibranch Point
164 (48.8178°, 125.1758°) and Prasiola Point (48.8169°, 125.1694°) have been systematically
165 emptied of all shore crabs each summer since 2000 and crabs > 20 mm have been removed.

166 Shore crabs observed during the emptying of the shelters and the small shore crabs that are
167 collected to replace them were carefully examined to make sure that they were *H. nudus* (Jensen
168 2014). Any *P. crassipes* that could be captured were preserved in 95% ethanol and some
169 collected between 1996 to 2003 were DNA-barcoded (Cassone and Boulding 2006) using
170 standard methods (Hebert et al. 2003b, 2003a).

171 **Sampling of *Pachygrapsus crassipes megalopae* larvae**

172 We present *P. crassipes* larval surveys that do not overlap in time at two sites: one near the
173 centre of its geographical range in Southern California and a second study at the northern end of
174 its range in Southern Oregon. In Southern California megalopae larvae were sampled daily using
175 a ‘tangle’ trap suspended from the end of the Scripps Institute of Oceanography pier
176 (32.866925°, 117.257481°) (Shanks 1983) which is located at the southern end of the Southern
177 California Bight. The end of the pier is 0.27 km from the beach. The trap consisted of a bundle of
178 hemp rope, looking like the head of a mop. A variety of late larval stages including megalopae
179 display high thigmokinesis, they cling to or associate with floating objects. The trap was held
180 away from the pier pilings by a long flexible fiberglass pole. The trap was suspended beneath the
181 lights at the end of the pier because the lights attracted larvae, which increased the size of the
182 daily catch (Shanks unpublished data). The trap was pulled from the water daily and shaken
183 vigorously in a bucket of seawater, which removed nearly all of the associated animals (Shanks
184 1983, 1985). Samples were returned to the laboratory where they were immediately sorted and
185 counted live. Sampling commenced on 20 July 1982 and continued through 19 July 1984 hence,
186 the sampling included the entire 1982/1983 El Niño (Shanks 2006). The original purpose of the
187 study was to investigate whether shoreward transport of megalopae was correlated with tidally-
188 generated internal waves using time series analysis (Shanks 1983). Here we use the time series of

189 megalopae abundance to determine when *P. crassipes* larvae were present in the coastal ocean in
190 the Southern California Bight.

191 In Southern Oregon, megalopae were sampled daily using light traps. These consisted of a 20
192 L clear plastic water bottle in which a fluorescent (years 1998-2001, 2006, 2007) or LED (years
193 2008-2019) light was suspended. Lights were on all night. Megalopae and other zooplankton
194 attracted to the light enter the trap through funnels (Roegner et al. 2007) and become trapped.
195 The trap was suspended from a floating dock (F dock) in the Charleston small boat harbor
196 (43.344634°, -124.320526°). The sample site was approximately 3.6 kilometers from the mouth
197 of the estuary. The trap was removed from the water daily and the water in the trap was drained
198 through a mesh cod end. The sample was returned to the laboratory and preserved with buffered
199 formalin for later analysis. Samples were inspected under a dissecting microscope and larvae
200 were identified using keys (Shanks 2001).

201 During the first four years of sampling in Charleston (1998-2001) samples were collected
202 daily over most or all of each year. Sampling commenced on 2 April 1998 and continued through
203 1 October 2001. Between 2002 and 2005 no funding was available and therefore no samples
204 were collected. Starting in 2006, grant support was provided by the Oregon Dungeness Crab
205 Commission with the goal of studying the recruitment of the Dungeness crab, *Metacarcinus*
206 *magister* (Dana, 1852) formerly known as *Cancer magister* Dana, 1852, (Shanks and Roegner
207 2007; Rasmuson and Shanks 2020). Dungeness crab megalopae settle at the shore from roughly
208 April through September, hence, sampling was limited to this period. Sampling started 23 May
209 2006 when the funding commenced. In 2007 through 2015 and from 2017 through to the present,
210 sampling started on or around 1 April each year (Rasmuson and Shanks 2020). In 2016, during a
211 very strong El Niño event, daily sampling started on 8 January and continued through

212 September. With this earlier start of sampling we hoped to test if *P. crassipes* megalopae were
213 again present along the coast as had been the case in 1998, the previous very strong El Niño
214 event.

215 **Predation Experiments**

216 If *P. crassipes* was to permanently extend its range northward, prey species in the upper
217 intertidal would be exposed to a new, predatory shore crab that is specialized for breaking hard-
218 shelled prey (Lord and Barry 2017), can run faster, and is behaviourally and physiologically
219 adapted to conditions in the upper shore (Hiatt 1948; Bovbjerg 1960; Lau and Martinez 2003)
220 relative to local shore crab species (Behrens Yamada and Boulding 1996, 1998). Upper intertidal
221 molluscs with thin shells especially those that lack a pelagic larval dispersal phase would be
222 most vulnerable to local extirpation (Vermeij 1977b, 1978, 1987). To test this idea, we set up
223 trials to compare the vulnerability of two prey species that coexist from Alaska to Coos Bay
224 Oregon: the thick-shelled checkered periwinkle, *Littorina scutulata* Gould, 1849, which has a
225 pelagic larval stage, and the thin-shelled *L. sitkana*, which has direct development. Although the
226 geographic range of *L. sitkana* ends in Southern Oregon, the geographical range of *L. scutulata*
227 extends south to Baja California. Since the southern part of the range of *L. scutulata* broadly
228 overlaps with that of *P. crassipes*, this prey species was expected to be less susceptible to this
229 predator. To test this hypothesis, we set up laboratory trials in a water table at South Slough
230 National Estuarine Research Reserve in Coos Bay, Oregon. The first experiment was designed to
231 determine the critical sizes of *L. scutulata* and *L. sitkana* - above which successful predation by
232 *P. crassipes* became unlikely (Boulding 1984; Palmer 1990) - as a function of the claw propal
233 height which is highly correlated with claw gape (Behrens Yamada and Boulding 1998).

234 The second experiment was designed to determine the consumption rate of medium and large
235 size classes of *L. sitkana* for crabs of varying sizes and to document how snail opening
236 techniques differed for different ratios of minimum snail diameter to crab claw size (Hughes and
237 Elner 1979; ap Rheinallt et al. 1985; Lawton and Hughes 1985).

238 Thirty-two *P. crassipes*, varying in size from 24-40 mm in carapace width, were trapped from
239 along the shore of the Charleston Boat Basin (43.3466°, -124.3284°). Twenty were selected
240 based on size, with the goal of testing a large range of crab sizes. Crab size (carapace width and
241 weight), claw propal height, and sex were recorded for each crab. Crabs were placed into
242 individual plastic sandwich containers (5 x 15 x 15 cm) which had been modified by hotmelt
243 gluing fly-screen mesh with 1.1 mm openings over windows cut into the two opposite sides of
244 the containers. The containers were then placed into a seawater table with a flow rate of
245 approximately 3 liters per minute with the salinity varying from 32.4-32.6 PSU, and temperature
246 varying from 14 to 17°C. Crabs were starved for at least 48 hours before the start of feeding
247 trials. *Littorina scutulata* and *L. sitkana* were opportunistically collected, identified to species by
248 experienced observers and held in the seawater table until the two predation experiments began.
249 Only healthy snails that actively retracted into their shells when prodded were used.

250 Critical size experiment - Five *L. scutulata* of varying size (6.7 to 13.3 mm) were selected and
251 placed into each container. Each time we checked the containers, we removed all shell
252 fragments, recorded the sizes of consumed snails, and replaced them with larger snails. From this
253 we determined the maximum size of *L. scutulata* that a particular crab was able to open and
254 consume within a 2-3 day period. The subsequent experiment with *L. sitkana* used only 3 snails
255 per container as this made it easier to determine the maximum size of snails being consumed.

256 Consumption rate experiment - Trials for the prey consumption rate followed a similar protocol.
257 Twenty-five *P. crassipes* of different sizes were each offered either 20 small *L. sitkana* (7.0-9.9
258 mm shell height) or 20 large *L. sitkana* (10.0-13 mm shell height). The experiment was
259 monitored every 2-3 days and the number of snails consumed was noted. Shell fragments were
260 removed and a prey opening technique was attributed to each consumed snail. Prey opening
261 techniques were classified as: 1) pull (snail removed with no damage to shell), 2) lower whorl
262 peel (chipping of shell edge), 3) upper whorl peel (hole in upper shell), or 4) crush (only shell
263 fragments left) (Fig. S1). Additional snails of the same size-class were added to the box to
264 maintain a total of 20 snails. The experiment continued for two weeks. In nearly all cases more
265 snails were offered than the crabs could consume, however, in three instances (of the 113 trials) a
266 crab was able to consume all 20 snails in a box between observations. These three cases were
267 from trials where large crabs offered the small size-class of snails. Effects of crab carapace
268 width, propal height and snail size-class on consumption rate per day were tested with a general
269 linear mixed model using SPSS v26 MIXED procedure. The individual crabs were the “subject”
270 (random effect), the propal height of the crab was a fixed covariate, the dependent variable was
271 the number of snails consumed within 24 hrs. Sex and snail size-class were included as fixed
272 effects in early versions of the model but were removed from the final model because $p > 0.25$.

273 Results

274 Temporary range expansions of *Pachygrapsus crassipes*

275 Our Bamfield dataset showed a time lag between a major El Niño and temporary range
276 extensions of *P. crassipes*. Figure 1A shows the number of *P. crassipes* observed at permanent
277 field sites near Bamfield Marine Sciences Centre between 1990 and 2019. Detailed field

278 observations began in 1993 but no *P. crassipes* were detected until July 1997 when a single crab
279 was observed. Adult crabs became much more abundant in 2000, 2-3 years after the major El
280 Niño of 1997-1998 (Fig. 1B). No crabs were seen between 2004 and 2015. Small adult crabs
281 again became abundant in the winter of 2016, 2 years after the major El Niño of 2014-2016.

282 Thirty or more *P. crassipes* adults were collected from Charleston Oregon in the summers of
283 2003 by B. Cassone (Cassone and Boulding 2006), 2005 by H.- J. Lee (McCarthy 1996) and
284 2019 by S.S. (this study). Sightings on the Central Oregon coast, around Newport and Boiler
285 Bay, are also not unusual (Table S1) suggesting that megalopae arrived there during El Niño
286 years. On the other hand, megalopae abundance, at the Hatfield Marine Science Center (HMSC)
287 in Newport, Oregon increased after strong El Niño (warm) events and, when abundant, decreased
288 after unusually strong La Niña (cold) events (Table S1). In 1986, after the very strong 1982-1983
289 El Niño, Erin Peters found an average of six *P. crassipes*/m² on a boulder beach at HMSC.
290 Michelle Moore, an aquarist at HMSC reports that prior to a 10-day deep freeze in February
291 1989, which took place during a large La Niña event, she collected *P. crassipes* to feed to the
292 aquarium's octopus, but after the freeze she could not find any. A number of the professional
293 biologists surveyed continued to actively look for *P. crassipes* but found only a few in
294 subsequent years. While temporary populations of *P. crassipes* were reported on the Central
295 Oregon coast, no sightings north of Boiler Bay were reported before 1983.

296 Range expansions of *P. crassipes* into northern Oregon, Washington, and British Columbia
297 can be linked to very strong El Niño events (Table S1, <https://ggweather.com/enso/oni.htm>.)
298 Ladd Johnson, then a graduate student at the University of Washington, reported seeing *P.*
299 *crassipes* at Tatoosh Island on the northern Washington coast from 1983-1985, shortly after the
300 very strong 1982-1983 El Niño. This El Niño is also linked to the sighting of *P. crassipes* in

301 1984 at Ecola State Park in northern Oregon (Jensen 1995). The strong 1991-1992 El Niño was
302 followed by sightings in Grays Harbour and Ozette, Washington, the weak El Niño of 1994-1995
303 to the sighting of one crab at Bamfield and the very strong 1997-1998 El Niño to frequent
304 sightings of *P. crassipes* at Bamfield and elsewhere. The most recent very strong El Niño of
305 2014-2016 is linked to high abundances of *P. crassipes* in Willapa Bay, Ozette, WA, and
306 Bamfield BC, as well as a new temporary range expansions north into Nootka Sound, BC and
307 east along the Strait of Juan de Fuca, at Neah Bay, WA and Shipwreck Point, WA (Table S1).

308 **Sampling of *Pachygrapsus crassipes* larvae**

309 In Southern California, *P. crassipes* megalopae were caught during both years in which
310 sampling took place (Fig. 2). Peak catches occurred from mid-August to mid-March in
311 1982/1983 and from the beginning of November through mid-April in 1983/1984. Few
312 megalopae were caught during the spring and summer. About twice as many megalopae were
313 caught in the 1983/1984 sample-year (56,441) than in the 1982/1983 sample-year (28,768).

314 In Oregon, daily sampling of *P. crassipes* megalopae started 2 April 1998 and lasted until 1
315 October 2001. *Pachygrapsus crassipes* megalopae were present in the samples from April 2 until
316 about Day of the Year (DOY) 150 (30 May) (Fig. 2). We caught 72 megalopae during the initial
317 pulse. No megalopae were caught after 30 May until the fall of 1998. In the 1998/1999
318 recruitment-season, we caught the first megalopae on DOY 305 (1 Nov, 1998). Catch peaked
319 during the winter months of December 1998 through mid-March 1999, few megalopae were
320 caught after March, catch dropped to zero after DOY 161 (10 June) and the total catch during
321 this period was 1,137 megalopae. In the 1999/2000 recruitment-season we caught one megalopae
322 on 27 Feb 2000. In the 2000/2001 sample-season, the first megalopae was caught on 8 January

323 2001 (DOY 8) and the last megalopae on 1 March (DOY 60). A total of 27 megalopae were
324 caught.

325 In 2016, the first *P. crassipes* megalopae were caught shortly after sampling commenced (8
326 January) and megalopae continued to be caught in appreciable numbers through DOY 103 (12
327 April). During this period, we caught 938 megalopae. In 2016, assuming a four-month
328 planktonic larval duration (PLD), the megalopae we caught likely started their pelagic period
329 between September and December of the previous year. As in the trap data from Southern
330 California, catch was highly pulsed (Fig. 3). For example, 38% of the megalopae caught during
331 the roughly six months of sampling were caught on just five days.

332 In each of the years in which we caught substantial numbers of *P. crassipes* megalopae (1998,
333 1999, and 2016, Fig 3), peak abundance of megalopae occurred during the winter months with
334 megalopae caught through the spring. In 2000 and 2001, when we sampled all year, and the
335 catch of *P. crassipes* was very low (1 and 27 total catch, respectively), we caught no megalopae
336 after DOY 60 (1 March). Between 2007-2015 and 2017-2019, sampling with the light trap for *M.*
337 *magister* megalopae commenced around 1 April (DOY 90), hence, if *P. crassipes* megalopae had
338 been present and abundant in these years as they were in 1998, 1999 and 2016 we should have
339 caught at least low numbers in the spring, but we caught none.

340 **Predation Experiments**

341 **Critical size experiment** –Claw propal height increased with carapace width significantly faster
342 for male crabs than for female crabs (Fig. S2). Therefore, to allow males and female crabs to be
343 analyzed together, all size comparisons were done using “propal” height. The maximum shell
344 length of *L. sitkana* opened was between 10-13 mm whereas the maximum shell length of the

345 thicker-shelled *L. scutulata* opened was 6-8 mm (Fig. 4). Most crabs were unable to successfully
346 attack *L. scutulata*. The exception was two male crabs that each ate one 6.5 mm *L. scutulata*
347 (Fig. 4).

348
349 **Consumption rate experiment** – Crabs with larger propal heights opened and ate snails at a
350 higher rate (Fig. S3). There was considerable variation in consumption rates of *L. sitkana* among
351 individual crabs (Fig. S4 and S5). Several crabs ate 8 to 12 per day of the 7-10 mm size-class and
352 up to 6 per day of the 10-13 mm size-class (Fig. 5). Large crabs ate more snails per day than
353 smaller crabs (Table 1; Fig. 5, Fig. S5). Larger crabs tended to completely crush or peel the
354 upper whorl whereas smaller crabs tended to pull or peel from the bottom edge (Fig. 6, Fig. S1).
355 Many crabs tried a number of techniques before successfully gaining access to snail body tissue.
356 A number of snails were observed with intact shells, but no operculum, suggesting that removal
357 of the operculum could be the first step of attacks that the crabs initiated at the shell aperture.

358 Discussion

359 **Temporary range extensions of *P. crassipes***

360 We present evidence that order of magnitude winter increases in megalopa larvae off coastal
361 Southern Oregon during two very strong El Niño events: 1997-1998 and 2014-2016 was the
362 result of poleward transport and subsequent recruitment in Washington and BC. We
363 acknowledge that the two *P. crassipes* megalopae time-series datasets used somewhat different
364 sampling methods and are from two different locations but combined together they clearly show
365 an order of magnitude or more increase during the winters of very strong El Niño years relative
366 to non-El Niño years. High abundances of *P. crassipes* megalopa larvae inside the Southern

367 California Bight during the winter period of the 1983 El Niño event (Fig. 2, Shanks 1983) were
368 followed by reports of intertidal *P. crassipes* juveniles in northern Oregon and northern
369 Washington shores (Table S1). In the El Niño year with higher catches megalopae were observed
370 in California into April. In the non-El Niño year no megalopae were observed after March. We
371 also present evidence that there was a high abundance of *P. crassipes* megalopa larvae off
372 Oregon during the 1998 El Niño event when sampling was continuous (Fig. 3),(Rasmuson and
373 Shanks 2020). After a time-lag of about one to four years after the El Niño events, this
374 abundance of the larvae was followed by reports of *P. crassipes* juveniles and adults at two
375 Bamfield field sites, as well as at Grays Harbor (Table S1). The size of the time lag is not
376 unexpected given that three to four years are required for *P. crassipes* to reach full adult size in
377 California (Hiatt 1948).

378 Both the range expansion and abundance of *P. crassipes* from northern Oregon to British
379 Columbia, appear to be linked to ocean currents that transported its larvae from permanent
380 populations in California to initiate temporary populations further north. Northward transport is
381 especially favourable during El Niño events when the poleward winter Davidson Current is
382 augmented by the warm coastal Kelvin wave generated by the El Niño. Poleward current
383 velocities in the Davidson current can reach average velocities of over 40 km/day during a strong
384 El Niño (Kosro 2002).

385 The pelagic larval phase in *P. crassipes* has been estimated to be three to four months
386 (Schlotterbeck 1976). If we assume a four-month larval phase then in 1982/1983, larvae were
387 likely present and abundant in the Southern California Bight coastal waters (Fig. 2) from roughly
388 mid-April 1982 through mid-March 1983 (almost 12 months) and in 1983/1984 they were likely
389 present and abundant in northern Oregon and Washington from July 1983 through mid-April

390 1984 (about 10 months) to have seeded *P. crassipes* juvenile populations at Ecola State Park,
391 WA and Tatoosh Island, WA (Table S1).

392 Ephemeral adult populations of *P. crassipes* in Central Oregon, Washington, and BC.
393 followed very strong El Niño events that transported megalopae north from California.
394 Megalopae were caught in Coos Bay, Oregon only in the winter and early spring prior to the
395 spring transition in the coastal winds and the highest catches were associated with the 1997-1998
396 and the 2016 El Niño events. *P. crassipes* is abundant in the Southern California Bight and this is
397 likely the source of the larvae sampled at Coos Bay; larvae released into the Bight are carried
398 northward in the winter months by the Davidson Current and by coastal currents associated with
399 El Niño events as has previously been described for the green crab (Behrens Yamada and Kosro
400 2010; Behrens Yamada et al. 2015).

401 Despite the periodic recruitment of *P. crassipes* megalopae to the Pacific Northwest coast,
402 self-sustaining adult populations of have not developed along the open coast. *Pachygrapsus*
403 *crassipes* has also not formed satellite populations in the numerous ‘inland’ waters of this region.
404 We have two hypotheses that could explain these observations that could be tested in subsequent
405 studies. The first hypothesis is that the sea surface temperatures on the wave-exposed open
406 coasts of BC to central Oregon are ordinarily too low to allow the zoea larvae of *P. crassipes* to
407 develop into megalopae during non-El Niño years. The second is that the larval behaviour and
408 long PLD of *P. crassipes* does not result in their retention inside the warmer regions of bays and
409 inlets of this region including the less saline Salish Sea (comprising Juan de Fuca Strait, the
410 Strait of Georgia, and Puget Sound), (Thomson 1981).

411 Our first hypothesis could be tested by comparing the effect of sea surface temperatures on
412 the PLD of *P. crassipes* with that of other crab species from the Pacific Northwest at salinities

413 typical of the outer and the Salish Sea. Female *P. crassipes* with eggs containing viable zoea
414 have been collected from the intertidal zone in Bamfield (Table S1). This suggests the pelagic
415 larval stage may be temperature-limited and therefore sensitive to temporary or permanent
416 changes in sea surface temperature (Marshall et al. 2011).

417 Our second hypothesis that *P. crassipes* larvae released by into a bay or estuary have not
418 evolved behaviour that result in retention has been supported by some field studies (DiBacco et
419 al. 2001; Miller and Morgan 2013). Field studies have supported larval retention behaviour for
420 the European green crab which swims vertically towards the bottom on an ebb tide and towards
421 the surface on a flood tide (Zeng and Naylor 1996; Banas et al. 2009; DiBacco and Therriault
422 2015). Consequently *P. crassipes* larvae from temporary satellite populations may be exported to
423 the coastal waters where coastal currents will carry them away from the adult population (Shanks
424 and Eckert 2005) during the long period of time before they become a megalopa larva. Larval
425 behaviour can evolve to adapt to local ocean current patterns but this is less likely in a highly-
426 dispersing species like *P. crassipes* which only shows a small amount of population genetic
427 structure at Point Conception (Cassone and Boulding 2006).

428 Retention of *P. crassipes* larvae might be more likely in the Salish Sea because of the longer
429 residence time of water there (Thomson 1981). If a satellite *P. crassipes* population were to
430 become established within the Straits of Juan de Fuca, then *P. crassipes* larvae from the satellite
431 population might spread throughout the inland sea as has recently been observed for the
432 European green crab (Behrens Yamada et al. 2017).

433 **Relative vulnerability of *L. sitkana* to native and invading shore crabs**

434 Our experiments suggest that *L. sitkana* has a size-refuge from the native purple shore crab, *H.*
435 *nudus*, but does not have a size refuge from *P. crassipes*. The predation experiments showed that
436 *L. scutulata* could reach a critical size of shell length (6-8 mm) beyond which it was invulnerable
437 to all but the largest male *P. crassipes*, which had propal height of 17 mm. However, the thinner-
438 shelled *L. sitkana* of 10-13 mm in shell length were still vulnerable to even the smaller *P.*
439 *crassipes* (propal heights of 7-10 mm) used in the critical size experiment. This differs from
440 previously published experiments where *H. nudus* with a propal heights up to 14.3 mm
441 completely avoided preying on *L. sitkana* of the 11-13 mm size-class (Appendix A in Behrens
442 Yamada and Boulding 1998). This difference in critical sizes suggests that *P. crassipes* is a more
443 specialized predator on gastropods than is the native shore crab species *H. nudus* (Zipser and
444 Vermeij 1978). The consumption rates of *L. sitkana* of up to 6-8 per day by *P. crassipes* (offered
445 7-10 mm snails) were substantially higher than those observed for *H. nudus* (offered 8-10 mm
446 snails) of 0.5 – 0.7 per day (Fig. 5 in Behrens Yamada and Boulding 1998). We acknowledge
447 that the two experiments are not entirely comparable because the native shore crabs were offered
448 a choice of smaller and larger *L. sitkana* whereas the *P. crassipes* in the current experiment were
449 only offered a single size-class of *L. sitkana*.

450 In Spain, intense selection by *P. marmoratus*, the marbled shore crab, has resulted in the
451 evolution of a very large and thick-shelled “crab”-resistant ecotype of *L. saxatilis* (Rolán-
452 Alvarez et al. 1997). The crab ecotype delays sexual maturity until a shell length of 8-10 mm
453 when it is beyond the critical size of all but the largest crabs (Boulding et al. 2017). We observed
454 the potential for *P. crassipes* to exert strong selection for increased size and shell thickness on *L.*
455 *sitkana* populations on wave-exposed shores which could result in evolutionary rescue of these
456 populations. However, large *L. sitkana* tethered on wave-protected shores experience higher

457 predation than smaller *L. sitkana* from large subtidal crabs (Behrens Yamada and Boulding
458 1996) and from the pile perch (McCormack 1982; Boulding et al. 1999, 2001) suggesting that
459 selection for later maturity would likely be opposed by selection for earlier maturity (Rochette
460 and Dill 2000).

461 *Littorina. sitkana* has a spatial refuge in the upper intertidal from the native purple shore crab,
462 *H. nudus*, as well as native subtidal crabs that forage in the intertidal (Behrens Yamada and
463 Boulding 1996). However, because *P. crassipes* forages higher up in the intertidal than does *H.*
464 *nudus* its invasion would reduce the amount of predator-free space available to prey populations
465 (Barrios-O'Neill et al. 2014) . Therefore, the permanent presence of *P. crassipes* would greatly
466 restrict the distribution of *L. sitkana*, making many current populations not viable. In addition the
467 indigenous shore crabs, *H. nudus* and *H. oregonensis* (Dana, 1851), could be displaced from
468 natural shelters by the competitively superior *P. crassipes* as has been demonstrated in California
469 where all three crab species overlap (Hiatt 1948; Willason 1981). We observed *P. crassipes*
470 inhabiting concrete shelters (Table S1) that were built for *H. nudus* (Boulding et al. 2007).

471 **Effects of permanent range expansion of *P. crassipes* on northern intertidal communities**

472 To assess the impact of a permanent range expansion of *P. crassipes* into the Pacific
473 Northwest it is useful to compare intertidal molluscs from north of Cape Argo, Oregon with
474 those that successfully coexist with *P. crassipes* further south. Another thin-shelled, direct-
475 developing species, *L. subrotundata* (Carpenter, 1864) that is highly vulnerable to predation by
476 the indigenous shore crab, *H. nudus* (Boulding and Van Alstyne 1993; Boulding et al. 1999,
477 2007) - is abundant only where foraging predatory crabs are rare which includes very wave-
478 exposed shores and salt marshes from Alaska to California (Reid 1986; Kyle and Boulding
479 1998). Between Cape Argo, OR and Laguna Manuela, Baja Mexico *Pachygrapsus crassipes*

480 coexists with a very high intertidal littorinid species, *L. keenae* (formerly *planaxis*) (Behrens
481 Yamada 1977a, 1977b; Lee and Boulding 2007) that has benthic egg masses and a
482 planktotrophic larva (Reid 1986). Feeding experiments suggest that the thick-shell and large size
483 of *L. keenae* results in it being even more resistant to *P. crassipes* predation than is *L. scutulata*.
484 When 50 *L. scutulata* and 50 *L. sitkana* of similar sizes were offered to 25 *P. crassipes*, 98% of
485 the *L. scutulata* survived predation but only 62% of the *L. sitkana* did (unpublished data, SBY,
486 July 1989). A similar feeding trial between *L. keenae* and *L. sitkana* yielded 100% survival for *L.*
487 *keenae*, but only 30% for *L. sitkana* (Ed Mastro, unpublished data, Cabrillo Marine Museum,
488 1990). These feeding experiments, combined with the data from our current study, suggest that
489 the colonization of the Salish Sea by *P. crassipes* could result in the extirpation of poorly-
490 defended prey populations that are dependent on successful local reproduction.

491

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502

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- 746

747 Tables

748 Table 1. General linear mixed model with the individual crabs as the “subject” (random effect)
 749 using SPSS v26 MIXED procedure. Dependent variable was the number of snails consumed
 750 within 24 hrs. The claw propal height of the crab was a fixed covariate. This simpler model fit as
 751 well (BIC = 571.64) as alternate models that also included crab sex (BIC= 570.28) or also
 752 included the two size-classes of the snails (BIC=568.94).

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Intercept	1	111	8.742	0.004
Propal_height	1	111	43.017	<0.001

Descriptive Statistics

	Count	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
Snails_consumed_24hrs	113	3.2853	3.45680	105.2%
Propal_height	113	11.748	3.4636	29.5%

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756 Figures captions

757 Fig. 1. A. Counts of *Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840 near Bamfield, BC between 1993
758 and 2019. B. Oceanic Niño Index Area 3.4. with a 3 month running average.

759

760 Fig. 2. Daily catch of *Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840 megalopae in a ‘tangle’ trap fished
761 from the end of the Scripps Institute of Oceanography pier in the Southern California Bight
762 during the 1983 El Niño event (1982-1984).

763

764 Fig. 3. Daily catch of *Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840 megalopae in a light trap deployed
765 in Coos Bay, Oregon. The upper row of the figure show data from the early work when sampling
766 was year-round. In 1998, sampling began on 2 April. Megalopae were caught each year with
767 large catches in 1998, 1999, and 2016. Major El Niño events occurred in 1997/1998 and
768 2015/2016 (Fig. 1B).

769

770 Fig. 4. Maximum size of *Littorina scutulata* Gould, 1849, and *L. sitkana* Philippi, 1846
771 consumed over a period of 2-3 days by male and female *Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840
772 as a function of claw propal height.

773

774 Fig. 5. Mean consumption rate of medium and large size-classes of *Littorina sitkana* by
775 *Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840 as a function of claw propal height (Table 1).

776

777 Fig. 6. Methods used to gain access to tissues of the medium and large size-classes of *Littorina*
778 *sitkana* as a function of claw propal height of *Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840 (See text
779 and Fig. S5).

780

781

P. crassipes megalopae caught per day

Supplementary material

Table S1. Summary of lined shore crab (*Pachygrapsus crassipes*) sightings with carapace width (c.w.), if measured, north of Coos Bay, Oregon (OR), USA, as compiled through interviews conducted by Sylvia Behrens Yamada (S.B.Y.) in 1990, and from notes by Greg Jensen, Brett Dumbauld, Armand Kuris, Jim Carlton, and Elizabeth Grace Boulding (E.G.B.). Range expansions 1–4 years after an El Niño (<https://ggweather.com/enso/oni.htm>, accessed 2 October 2020) are indicated, with strength designated by asterisks (*, moderate; **, strong; ***, very strong).

Northern range	Latitude (°N)	Year	Comment	Reference	Prior El Niño?
Coos Bay, OR	43.3	1968	Present	Ricketts and Calvin 1968	1965–1966**
Coos Bay, OR	43.3	1980	Compilation of existing knowledge	Morris et al. 1980	Unknown
Newport, OR	44.6		Present	Hiatt 1948	Unknown
Newport, OR	44.6	1968	“Northernmost” limit	Ricketts and Calvin 1968	1965–1966**
Boiler Bay, OR	44.8	1950	Present	Dale Snow, pers. comm., 1990	Unknown
Boiler Bay, OR	44.8	1969, 1970	Present	Armand Kuris, pers. comm., 2019	1965–1966**
Seal Rock tide pools, OR	44.5	1990	Not common	Vicki Osis, pers. comm., 1990	1987–1988**
Yaquina Head, OR, tide pools	44.7	1990	Not common	Vicki Osis, pers. comm., 1990	1987–1988**
Yaquina Head, Newport, OR	44.7	~1970 to 1990	Present sporadically	Jeff Gonor, pers. comm., 1990	Unknown
Newport, OR	44.6	1986	6/m ² at Hatfield Marine Science Center	Erin Peters, pers. comm., 1986	1982–1983***
Newport, OR	44.6	1988	Lots of crabs	Michelle Moore, pers. comm., 1990	1987–1988**
Newport, OR	44.6	1989	No crabs after 10-day deep-freeze in February 1989	Michelle Moore, pers. comm., 1990	1987–1988** followed by “strong” La Niña 1988–1989

Newport, OR	44.6	May 1990	One crab	Michelle Moore, pers. comm., 1990	1987–1988** followed by “strong” La Niña 1988–1989
Boiler Bay, OR	44.8	July 1990	One large crab in a long crack, mid-intertidal zone	Sally Walker, pers. comm., 1990	1987–1988** followed by “strong” La Niña 1988–1989
Yaquina Head, OR	44.7	June 1990	No crabs	Kathy Liska, pers. comm., 1990	1987–1988** followed by “strong” La Niña 1988–1989
Seal Rock, OR	44.5	June 1990	One crab	Kathy Liska, pers. comm., 1990	1987–1988** followed by “strong” La Niña 1988–1989
Newport, OR, Sawyer’s Landing	44.6	1991	Three crabs	S.B.Y.	1987–1988** followed by “strong” La Niña 1988–1989
Yaquina Head, OR	44.6	1991	Two on south side	Kathy Liska, pers. comm., 1991	1987–1988** followed by “strong” La Niña 1988–1989
Yaquina Head, OR	44.6	1992	Present	S.B.Y.	1991–1992**
Ecola State Park, OR	45.9	May 1984	Present	Jensen 1995	1982–1983***
Tatoosh Island, Washington (WA)	48.4	1983–1985	Present	Ladd Johnson, pers. comm., 2007	1982–1983***
Willapa Bay, WA, Tokeland Marina	46.7	1998	Present	Brett Dumbauld, pers. comm., 2019	1994–1995*
Grays Harbor, WA, Westport	46.9	Prior to 2005	Present	Lamb and Handby 2005	Unknown
Willapa Bay, WA	46.7	2019	Present	Steve Shotwell, pers. comm., 2019	2014–2016***
Strait of Juan de Fuca, WA, Neah Bay, boat ramp, and Shipwreck Point	48.4	May 2018	Common along shore of Strait of Juan de Fuca, more than one age class present	Armand Kuris, pers. comm., 2019	2014–2016***

Ozette, WA	48.1	1995	North end of Yellow Banks	Jeff Goddard, pers. comm., 1995	1991–1992**
Ozette, WA	48.1	July 2019	All sizes, including ovigerous females	Greg Jensen, pers. comm., 2019	2014–2016***
Bamfield, British Columbia (BC)	48.8	1993–1996	No crabs	E.G.B.	1991–1992**
Bamfield, BC	48.8	July 1997	One male, c.w. 26.5 mm, Second Beach	Emma Hay and E.G.B. (Appendix II in McCarthy 1996)	1994–1995*
Bamfield, BC	48.8	1999	One male, c.w. 31.5 mm, Prasiola Point	E.G.B. and Emma Hay (Appendix II in McCarthy 1996)	1997–1998***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	2000	Twenty-seven observed, c.w. 22–30.7 mm, Second Beach region	E.G.B. field notes (Appendix II in McCarthy 1996)	1997–1998***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	2001	Two observed, c.w. 26–30 mm	E.G.B. (Appendix II in McCarthy 1996)	1997–1998***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	2002	Three observed including male, c.w. 15.9 mm, on Maben’s Beach	E.G.B. (Appendix II in McCarthy 1996)	1997–1998***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	2003	Twelve observed including ovigerous females on Second Beach and Dixon Island	Bryan Cassone and E.G.B. (Appendix II in McCarthy 1996)	2002–2003*
Bamfield, BC	48.8	2004–2015	No crabs	E.G.B.	2002–2003*, 2009–2010*
Bamfield, BC	48.8	August 2016	Two crabs from Bamfield Inlet, c.w. 9–11 mm	E.G.B., Paige Stuart, Rose Boulding	2014–2016***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	28 December 2016	Captured 7 males, c.w. 14.7–32.0 mm, and 1 female, c.w. 18.5 mm	Emily Merlo and Megan Baker	2014–2016***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	26–28 July 2017	Twelve crabs observed or captured, c.w. 17.5–21 mm	E.G.B., Kerstin Riley, and Ashley Riley	2014–2016***

Bamfield, BC	48.8	December 2017	One observed in crack	E.G.B., Kerstin Riley, and Ashley Riley	2014–2016***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	August 2018	One ovigerous female, c.w. 30 mm	E.G.B., Paige Stuart, and Caitlyn Burry	2014–2016***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	December 2018	One observed in crack	E.G.B., Kerstin Riley, and Ashley Riley	2014–2016***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	August 2019	Six captured, c.w. 17–34 mm, plus ovigerous female, c.w. 31 mm	E.G.B., Paige Stuart, and Caitlyn Burry	2014–2016***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	December 2019	One observed in crack	E.G.B., Kerstin Riley, and Ashley Riley	2014–2016***
Bamfield, BC	48.8	August 2020	No crabs observed	E.G.B., Paige Stuart, and Caitlyn Burry	2014–2016***
Nootka Sound, BC	49.8	August 2016	Five captured, many observed in cracks	E.G.B. and Emma Hay	2014–2016***
Nootka Sound, BC	49.8	August 2018	Two in cracks	E.G.B. and Emma Hay	2014–2016***

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Fig. S1. Classification of shell fragments of Sitka periwinkle (*Littorina sitkana*). Scale bar represents 5 mm. (A) Peeled starting at lip of aperture; (B) damage to body whorl; (C) body tissues extracted by pulling. (Figure 2.4 in Hauck (2020), reproduced with permission.)

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Fig. S2. Linear regression showing relationship between claw propal height and carapace width of individual lined shore crabs (*Pachygrapsus crassipes*). Each sex is shown in a separate colour.

Fig. S3. Number of Sitka periwinkle (*Littorina sitkana*) consumed by individual lined shore crabs (*Pachygrapsus crassipes*) for each 24 h replicate period in the laboratory consumption experiment. Each sex is shown as a separate colour. Only the large size class of snails (10–13 mm) was analyzed here.

Fig. S4. Cumulative number of Sitka periwinkle (*Littorina sitkana*) consumed by individual lined shore crabs (*Pachygrapsus crassipes*) over their time in the laboratory consumption experiment. Each crab is shown as a separate line that shows the number of hours that it was part of the experiment. Dashed lines = female crabs; solid lines = male crabs; square symbols = small snails (7–10 mm); round symbols = large snails (10–13 mm).

Fig. S5. Number of Sitka periwinkle (*Littorina sitkana*) consumed by individual lined shore crabs (*Pachygrapsus crassipes*) for each 24 h replicate period in the laboratory consumption experiment. Each crab is shown as a separate colour.